

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

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Method responsible: Heike Link

1 Description of sampling gear

A multicorer (MC) or/and a giant box corer (BC) (by subsampling) will be used to collect sediment cores (10 cm i.d., 20-25 cm length) and bottom water (tbd l) at (tbd)sites, depth (tbd), and replicate (tbd). Additionally, CTD-rosette installed aboard R/V Polarstern will be use to sample bottom water.

The required equipment and materials (chemicals) for the corresponding measurement is listed below.

NO	Activity	Equipment- Material	Amount	Safety consideration
1	Sampling of bottom water	Canister (10 L)		
		Tube		
2	Sampling of sediment with Multicorer (MC)	Core liners		
		Oxygen Sensor spots		
		Core holders		
		Rubber plugs (top + bottom)		
		Running seawater		
		Buckets		
		Freshwater		
		Alu foil		
		Cap toe shoes		
		Helmets		
		Towel, cloth		
		Nitril gloves		
		Ruler		
3	Sampling of sediment with Box corer (BC)	Core liners		
		Syringes		
		Rubber plugs (top + bottom)		
		O-rings		
		Alu foil		

NO	Activity	Equipment- Material	Amount	Safety consideration
		White cap		
		Ruler		
4	Sediment core incubation	Acid-cleaned Syringes (60 ml) with tube		
		Alu foil		
		Stirring tops (rinsed with bw) + controller		
		Bucket or bowl		
		Fibox		
		Ruler		
5	Water (from incubation) filtration	Filter holders		
		Syringe		
		Tubes		
		15 ml vials		
		10% HCL		
		nanopure/milli Q water		
		GF/F Filters		
		Filter tweezers		
		Ethanol		
		Bucket		
		Alu foil		
		Ziplock		
		Sample slips		
		Tray or dish		
		Nitril gloves		
6	Sediment sieving	Ruler		
		Sieves		
		Container (500 ml)		
		4 % formaldehyde		

2 Sampling gear deployment

Deployment, calibration, and maintenance of MC, BC, and CTD should be performed according to standard routine of R/V Polarstern.

3 Sample sorting-collection-preservation procedure

Before deploying MC or BC, double-check the availability of the cold room for sediment storage and prepare the necessary equipment for sediment collection.

Sediment core sample collection

3.1.1 Sediment core for benthic fluxes and biodiversity assessment

3-U5 sediment cores from the MC or sub-sample from BC will be used.

3.1.2 Detail procedure for MC:

Safety

- Check if deck is slippery

helmets on?

- cap toe shoes
- Regarding safety pin in MC:--> release when MC over water; put back as soon as possible when MC reachable (no contact with the ship/ground!!!)

Preparation

Select 8 liners + put them into MC holders

- **Charge** top and bottom lids
- **pull safety pin when MC is lifted**

Deployment

- **Lower MC** at 0.3–0.5 m/s at great depths:max. 1.0 m/s)
- →take care that pressure on cable is constant
- Lower MC at 0.3 m/s to the seafloor(20-30m above the seafloor)
- **Upontouchdown**,give 3–5 m more cable at deep sea stations give 8m more cable)
- **Heaveslowly** (0.2–0.3 m/s)until liftoff (watch cable or cable drag display)
- After lift off **heave** MC at 0.5 m/s until sea surface
- Take cores from MC with rubber stoppers

- Measure sediment height; if > 25cm, adjustment needed.
- **Sit core onto its bottom**
- Adjustment: with top stopper vacuum control, let core glide down slowly, cut of extra sediment and slowly, steadily insert bottom by pushing the core liner onto it.
- slowly, steadily insert bottom by pushing the core liner onto it
- **Clean cores and bring** to temperature controlled room (2°C)

Sediment core samling with Multicorer (© H.Link)

3.1.3 Detail procedure for BC:

- Insert cores to ca. 15-25 cm into the sediment (you may want to mark a line in the core)
- Once the cores are pushed into the sediment, protect cores from external disturbance (sediment falling onto surface) – aluminum foil or white caps
- *Sampling order in the BC: push in big cores first, then syringes 60ml, syringes 10ml, in the end take surface sediments*
- Retrieve samples in the opposite order! Small syringes first, then larger, then the incubation cores
- reach/grab underneath the core (use the full hand to avoid core from falling out) to retrieve it from the BC

Box core sampling (© H.Link)

- Sit core onto its bottom and slowly, steadily insert bottom by pushing the core liner onto it. Make sure that the larger of the 2 O-rings on the bottom piece is up (and maybe slightly grease the O-ring with the grease in the repair box). You may need to remove the white cap while pushing, thus that air can escape from the core volume.
- Keep away from sun and bring cores as fast as possible into the cold room to prepare incubations

3.1.4 Sediment core for determination of sediment properties and pigment concentration

Additional (tbd)sub cores (tbd cm i.d., tbd cm leght) will be taken to later asses sediment solid phase, water content, and sediment pigment concentration.

- Store the surface sample (0-1 cm) in pre-weighed plastic vials and freeze immediately at -80 ° C for later sediment solid phase analysis and at -20 ° C for later pigment analysis

|Bottom water collection

Bottom water samples will be collected from MC, BC, or the ship's Niskin bottles. Sample will be filled into canister (10 L) and store in cold room (0.8 - 4° C) prior to incubation.

4 Sample analysis method

Sediment core incubation (cold room)

Sediment cores and bottom water will be incubated to measure benthic mineralization (sediment oxygen demand: SOD, silicic acid, nitrate, ammonium and phosphate) rates ($\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$). After incubation, the same sediment core will be used to assess species diversity, abundance, and biomass.

Illustration of the general sampling processing of microcosm incubations (Link and Piepenburg, 2013)

Sediment core incubations are performed in a dark and temperature controlled room ($0.8 - 4^{\circ} \text{C}$) for 24 – 72 h. SOD was determined as the decrease in oxygen concentrations in the water phase and was measured periodically (2 to 8 h intervals) with a non-invasive optical probe (Fibox 3 LCD, PreSens, Regensburg, Germany). To determine changes in nutrient concentrations, samples of the overlying water phase were taken at three times during the incubation, including the onset and end. Oxygen and nutrient fluxes are determined as the slope of the linear regression of the oxygen and nutrient concentration on incubation time and corrected for solute concentration in the replacement water.

The detail procedure is describe as follow:

Prior to the onset of incubation MC

- Put core onto extruder and push sediment up until height of overlying water phase is ~10cm at deep sea stations and 15 cm at shelf stations (300-400m)
- **Top** sediment cores with bw from 10-L canister; top as much as possible.
- **Fill control cores** (A,B,C) with bw water from MC (or rosette) at ~20 cm height
- Saturate each core (sampling cores, control core) and bw canister with O₂ with a bubbling system for 2 hours
- Let **acclimate** for **4-6h** (with stirring top loosely sitting on core)
- Fill control cores with bottom water; core with bottom O-ring and rubber stopper, lid with bubbling system

Prior to the onset of incubation BC

- Top sediment cores are **carefully** topped with bottom water collected at the same station; top as much as possible. To carefully top, let water run without any pressure along the wall of the core. You can use the infusion bags or a tube with an inverted pipette tip inserted at the end reaching into the water bucket.
- Saturate with oxygen in order to avoid suboxic conditions with a bubbling device. Make sure that the bubbling device does not touch the surface of the sediments
- let acclimate for six to eight hours with the stirring top loosely sitting on top of the core
- Prepare and label vials for water phase nutrient analysis (details below: filtration of water samples)
- label sediment core
- fill control chambers with bottom water and treat as sediment cores

BEFORE FIRST STATION

calibrate fibox with two-point-calibration (T is set manually between 0° -2°) Oxygen content set to % signal above 10 000

Onset of incubations

- Mix water phase carefully while removing the bubbling device (*no resuspension!*)
- Measure water temperature with Fibox sensor
- Nutrient samples:
 - Use 1 acid cleaned syringe per core
 - Take 15 ml of water phase for rinsing the syringe (you can use this water to rinse the stirring top)
 - Take 60 ml of water sample and keep syringe in the cold room until filtering

- Once the water sample has been taking, the incubations need to be closed
- Close incubations:
 - Carefully (but probably with force) insert the stirring top on the core
 - Avoid bubbles – it works well to keep the temperature hole at the highest point, while holding the incubation core slightly inclined
 - Set stirring motor on top
 - Adjust voltage of motors to avoid resuspension
 - Top up with bottom water if needed to remove air
 - Measure oxygen (and temperature, if not done yet) using the Fibox probe
 - Measure oxygen and temperature periodically (4-8 h intervals) until it has declined by 20 %
 - Three mini-incubations of macrofaunal-cleaned sediments were carried out in scintillation vials in parallel to general SOD

- At 90 % oxygen: midway nutrient sampling
 - Measure oxygen concentration and temperature
 - Take 15 ml of water sample for rinsing syringe
 - Take 60 ml of water sample
 - Refill core with rosette water to remove air. Use an additional syringe, that you rinse thoroughly before filling the core
 - Remeasure oxygen!

- End of incubations (80 % oxygen)
 - Measure oxygen and temperature
 - Measure water height and sediment height of each core, including controls
 - Take water sample (15 ml rinsing, 60 ml sample)
 - Keep cores in cold until sieving

Filtration of water samples for nutrient analyses from incubation water phase (cold room)

For safety measure, always wear PE gloves (no latex, no powder!) during rinsing, cleaning, and filtration.

4.2.1 *Preparation on land*

Before boarding, all material (filter holders, syringes, tubes, 15 ml vials) need to be prepared on land, acid washed (10% HCL v/v) for 48h, rinsed twice with distilled water, and twice with nanopure/milli Q water.

4.2.2 *Preparation on board before incubation*

- Prepare 15 ml vial:
 - 3 vials per core
 - Vials: keep a running number per core sample; 3 vials of one core are a,b,c; also mark station, oxygen percentage and core number on vial. E.g.
 - 1a
 - 301 - 1
 - 80%
 - Sediment cores are labeled with numbers (e.g. 1,2,3), control chamber with capital letters (A, B, C)
 - That makes a total of 66 vials per incubation (3 replicates x 3 oxygen levels x 6 cores + 3 of rosette water at 90 % oxygen + 9 for ammonium protocol)
 - You need 3 extra vials for the ammonium matrix effect and blank (see ammonium protocol)

Samples are taken (see incubation protocol)

1. At the onset of incubations
2. At ca. 90 % oxygen
3. At the end of incubations

Always leave samples (in syringes) in a dark, cold place before filtration starts

4.2.3 *Filtration*

- Prepare a clean working space with an aluminum 'napkin' in the lab. You can reuse the aluminum napkin, if it had been properly stored, and wiped with Ethanol and a kimwipe at working space installation
- Prepare 1 filter holder per syringe (usually 6 per filtration):
- Insert combusted GF/F filter into filter holder using Ethanol cleaned tweezers
- Get syringes with samples
- Screw filter onto syringe and rinse with 10 ml
- Rinse the 3 vials with 10 ml total sample water
- Fill vial a and b with 14 ml each, vial c with 6.0 ml

- Close vials tightly with caps
- Filter next syringe

4.2.4 *Sample storage*

- Store vials a and b to the -80 °C freezer until later nutrient analyses (nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, silicic acid; Autoanalyzer applying colorimetric methods adapted from Grasshoff et al.(1999))
- Follow Ammonium protocol for sample c
- Add 3 ml of NH₄-analyses to sample c as quickly as possible
- Store in the dark)at room temperature until reading (5-6 h after the initiation of colorimetric reaction) at fluorometer

4.2.5 *Post_Filtration*

- Rinse filter holders and syringes with 10 % HCl (after incubation) and 3 times with nanopure/milli Q
- Keep in a clean place or container

|Sieving (benthic lab)

After incubation, the same sediment cores were utilized for later analyses of species diversity, abundance, and biomass.

- Sieve first 5 cm of sediment core in a 'sink' like gold mining over a small round sieve – this is meant to avoid damaging the often very small infauna in the top layer of the sediments. Collect the residue from the small sieve before adding further sediments
- Sieve rest over big sieve (and/or small; depending on what you find easiest)
- Collect residues in 1 container (ca. 500ml) per core with 4 % buffered (seawater)formaldehyde

|Further analysis post expedition

4.4.1 *Nitrate, Nitrite, Phosphate, Silicic acid*

Frozen water sample (at -80 ° C) will be analyzed with an Autoanalyzer 3 (Bran and Luebbe) applying colorimetric methods adapted from Grasshoff et al. (1999).

4.4.2 *Sediment pigment concentration*

Chl a and phaeopigment concentrations will be determined fluorometrically following a modified protocol proposed by Riaux-Gobin and Klein (1993) as described in Link et al. (2011): two grams of wet substrate were extracted with 10mL 90% acetone (v/v) for 24h at 4 ° C, and the

supernatant was measured in a Turner Designs 20 fluorometer before and after acidification. Quantities are expressed as microgram pigment per gram of dry sediment $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$).

4.4.3 Porosity

Porosity will be determined from weight loss upon drying the sediment sample using a dry sediment density of 2.65gcm^{-3} (Berner, 1980). The weight difference between wet and dry sample will be corrected for salt from seawater content using the average seawater density and the value of salinity measured in the bottom waters.

4.4.4 $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ $\delta^{15}\text{N}$

Analysis for $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ will be carried out with a CF-IRMS (continuous-flow isotope ratio mass spectrometer) coupled to a Costech 4010 elemental analyzer. Prior to the analysis, ground sediments will be acidified twice for 48h with a dilute HCl solution to dissolve solid carbonates. The acid supernatant will be decanted and solids rinsed with nanopure water and dried. Data will be reported in standard notation in ‰ with respect to the V-PDB standard for carbon.

4.4.5 Total organic carbon (TOC) and Total nitrogen (TN)

Percentages of TOC and TN Will be determined with a Flash EA 1112+ MAS 200 elemental analyzer. Prior to combustion, sediment slices (1 cm) from the syringes will be freeze-dried and acidified with acid (2 % HCL) to remove the inorganic carbon.

4.4.6 Sediment grain size

Sediment grain size from wet sediments will be measured with a Malvern Mastersizer 2000 (Veit Köhler et al. 2018, Vanreusel et al. 2021b) or a Malvern Mastersizer 3000 (Säring et al. 2021b) with a particle size range 0.002–2000 μm . Results will be expressed as percentages of different size fractions according to Wentworth (1922).

4.4.7 Biomass

Taxon Identification

5 Raw and analyzed data formats

Raw data format will include date, station name, station label, gear, geographical position, water depth, bottom water salinity, bottom water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), dissolved oxygen, number of replicate for sediment core.

Processed data will have identity (named) according to its respective station. Processed data will contain variable and unit that are listed below.

Variable	Unit
O2 flux (SOD)	(mmol m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Nitrate flux	(mmol m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Nitrite flux	(mmol m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Ammonium flux	(mmol m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Phosphate flux	(mmol m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Silicic acid flux	(mmol m ⁻² d ⁻¹)
Chl a concentration	µg ⁻¹ dry sediment
Phaeopigments concentration	µg ⁻¹ dry sediment
Porosity	
δ 13C	‰
δ 15N	‰
Total organic carbon	%
Total nitrogen	%
Sediment grain size	µm - mm
Biomass	

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